

RL-Exponential-DAS: Exponential Decision Schedules for Dynamic Algorithm Selection – Supplementary Material

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1 Reward Study

In addition to the reward formulation introduced in the core part of the paper, we investigate three alternative reward definitions. All four formulations share the property of being agnostic to the global optimum (cf. Table 1). For each formulation, the reward at the initial checkpoint is set to

$$r_i = \log(s),$$

since no reference value is yet available. This choice encourages the agent to favor exploration-oriented algorithms in the first step.

To account for the fact that early and late checkpoints naturally yield reward distributions of different magnitudes, rewards are normalized separately at each checkpoint index using a running estimate of the mean and variance. Addressing this scale discrepancy is one of the key motivations behind the RL-Exponential-DAS formulation.

Table 1 summarizes the four reward definitions together with the AOCC metrics obtained on a portfolio \mathcal{P}_{het} in a LOPO scenario using $CDB = 1.5$. The agent trained with reward r_1 achieves the strongest performance.

2 Checkpoint Division Base Study – LOIO

The LOIO results (Fig. 1) closely mirror the LOPO results, both qualitatively and in terms of the magnitude of the AOCC gains. The main difference is that the $D = 3$ case becomes significant for most cdb values under LOIO, as expected from the smaller train/test gap of the instance-level split. The fact that LOPO and LOIO yield such similar conclusions departs from the standard observation in static AS, where LOPO is markedly harder. We attribute this to the nature of the learned policy: as discussed in Section 3, the agent learns a temporal exploration–exploitation schedule rather than a per-function specialization, and such a schedule transfers well even to unseen function classes.

Table 1: Evaluated reward formulations and their AOCC performance (\mathcal{P}_{het} , $CDB = 1.5$, LOPO scenario).

Reward	Formula	Explanation	AOCC
r_1	$\log\left(\text{clip}\left(\frac{\Delta_i}{s}, 0, 1\right) + \epsilon\right)$	Favors relative improvement rather than raw objective decrease and compresses rare large gains, stabilizing learning across problems with different scales.	0.633
r_2	$\text{clip}\left(\frac{\Delta_i}{s}, 0, 1\right)$	Similar to r_1 , but without logarithmic transformation.	0.618
r_3	$\begin{cases} \log(s), & \text{if } i < N \text{ (not final)} \\ \log\left(\frac{\Delta_i}{s} + \epsilon\right), & \text{if } i = N \text{ (final)} \end{cases}$	Provides a constant baseline reward during the optimization process, only evaluating and rewarding the total relative improvement from the initial best solution at the final checkpoint.	0.617
r_4	$\begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \frac{\Delta_i}{s} \geq 10^{-3} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$	A sparse, binary reward that encourages meaningful progress by yielding a value of 1 only when the immediate relative improvement exceeds a 0.1% threshold of the initial objective range.	0.619

3 Agent Analysis

The majority of studies on RL-based Meta-BBO evaluate the learned agent exclusively through aggregate performance metrics and provide little, if any, qualitative analysis of its behavior. We argue that inspecting the learned policy is an essential complement to such metrics, as it clarifies whether observed performance arises from a meaningful control strategy or from incidental regularities of the benchmark. In the case of RL-DAS, this question is of limited interest: the portfolio consists of closely related Differential Evolution variants, so the identity of the optimizer selected at a given stage carries little semantic content.

By contrast, the heterogeneous portfolio \mathcal{P}_{het} considered in this paper, we combine optimizers with markedly different search characteristics, ranging from the explorative behavior of SPSO and G3PCX to the exploitative behavior of LMCMAES. This qualitative heterogeneity makes the analysis of the learned policy substantive rather than descriptive, and enables a direct examination of how the exploration–exploitation trade-off is realized by the RL-Exponential-

Fig. 1: Effect of the checkpoint division base on AOCC under the LOIO protocol.

DAS agent. To this end, we recorded the action distribution produced by the policy network at every checkpoint on the held-out test instances and aggregated these distributions across folds and seeds. Figure 2 reports the resulting selection probabilities for $D=10$ and $cdb=1.0$, which is representative of the pattern observed across the remaining values of cdb in this dimensionality. A consistent temporal structure emerges: in the early checkpoints, the agent allocates most of its probability mass to the exploration optimizer (SPSO in this case), whereas in later checkpoints it progressively concentrates on LMCMAES. This behavior is consistent with the hypothesis underlying the design of RL-Exponential-DAS, namely that a competent meta-policy should focus on explorative optimizers early in the search, when landscape information is scarce, and transition towards an exploitative optimizer once a promising basin has been identified.

Fig. 2: Mean action-selection probabilities of the RL-Exponential-DAS policy per checkpoint, aggregated by BBOB function group ($D=10$, $cdb=1.0$).

A similar pattern can be observed for different values of cdb . Figure 3 presents the corresponding heatmap for $cdb = 2.1$. While the overall structure of the

schedule is preserved, the policy exhibits somewhat greater complexity: the agent initially selects G3PCX, transitions to PSO in the intermediate phase, and ultimately converges on LMCMAES for the late-stage checkpoints.

Fig. 3: Mean action-selection probabilities of the RL-Exponential-DAS policy per checkpoint, aggregated by BBOB function group ($D=10$, $cdb=2.1$).

3.1 Consistency of results

We evaluate policies across different function groups, problem dimensionalities, and values of cdb . A first observation is that the standard deviations are consistently low in all settings, indicating that the learned policies are stable across random seeds and cross-validation folds. This stability persists across different cdb values and experimental protocols.

In addition to the main figure for LOPO with $cdb = 2.1$, here we present analogous plots for LOPO with $cdb = 1.0$ and LOIO with $cdb = 2.1$. Although some variations are visible, two consistent patterns emerge. First, the case $D = 2$ exhibits qualitatively different behavior compared to higher-dimensional settings, with the learned policy being markedly more uniform. Second, in higher dimensions, the probability mass assigned to LMCMAES increases with larger checkpoint values. This increase is typically accompanied by a corresponding decrease in the probability of SPSO.

For $cdb = 1.3$, the early dominance of SPSO becomes especially pronounced in the higher-dimensional settings. As shown in Figure 6, for $D = 5$ and $D = 10$ the agent allocates the majority of its probability mass to SPSO across most checkpoints, with LMCMAES only catching up at the latest stages of the search.

Fig. 4: Mean policy probabilities per checkpoint for the RL-Exponential-DAS agent, with shaded regions indicating \pm one standard deviation across seeds (for $cdb=1.0$).

Fig. 5: Mean policy probabilities per checkpoint for the RL-Exponential-DAS agent, with shaded regions indicating \pm one standard deviation across seeds (for $cdb=2.1$) – LOIO.

Fig. 6: Mean policy probabilities per checkpoint for the RL-Exponential-DAS agent, with shaded regions indicating \pm one standard deviation across seeds (for $cdb=1.3$) – LOIO. SPSO dominates the early steps of the policy for $D = 5$ and $D = 10$.